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Data management plan (DMP)

Performance Comparison of kNN and GD

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1.0	2022-04-15	First version of DMP – created for start of project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published data sets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of data sets that will be reused or produced

Produced data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Training and Test Subsets for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD	structured text	CSV	1 MB	no
P2	Results for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD	images	PNG	1 MB	no
P3	Plots for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD	images	PNG	10 MB	no
P4	Datasets for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD	structured text	CSV, ARFF	1 MB	no
P5	Source Code for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD	source code	PYTHON 3	4 MB	no

There are no reused data sets.

1b Data generation and reuse

Data generation

External Data:

In this experiment two external datasets are used: fish and employee. The fish dataset is from kaggle.com, the employee dataset is from OpenML. In the following paragraph, the data this project uses and collects, are described:

The employee dataset is from openml.org and provides annual salary information including gross pay and overtime pay for all active, permanent employees of Montgomery County, MD paid in calendar year 2016. It is composed of 13 features and 9222 rows of data. The data is published under the Public Domain (CC0) and was last updated 2019-09-12. It is accessible in the ARFF format. This format describes its data as a list of instances sharing a set of attributes. It is an ASCII text file that is human readable and parsable by many ARFF parsers implemented in different programming languages, for this experiment we will use liac-arff for python.

Link to Page: <https://www.openml.org/d/42125>

Link to ARFF: <https://www.openml.org/data/download/21718841/dataset>

Save the file to: [evaluation/employee/data/employee.arff](#)

The fish dataset is from kaggle.com and provides records of 7 common different fish species in fish market sales. It is published under the GNU General Public License, version 2 and was created and last updated in 2019-06-13. We will use Version 2 of the fish dataset provided by SAS Ondemand for Academics. The file consists of 7 columns and has 159 rows of data. CSV is a widely used format to store data in a human readable format and its format is used.

Link to Page: <https://www.kaggle.com/aungpyaeap/fish-market>

Save the file to: [evaluation/fish/data/fish.csv](#)

The complete datasets (P4), as well as the test and training subsets (P1) will be published on Zenodo in case the original sources are not available anymore in the future.

Generated Data

The project will produce a python 3 implementation of the kNN and GD algorithm together with code to automate the evaluation of these algorithms against the state-of-the-art implementation of sklearn. The algorithms will use standard python packages as well as numpy to make use of advanced matrix calculations. The algorithms will be placed in the algorithms folder of the project. For each dataset, there is a python script called "predictor.py" which should be used to evaluate the algorithms against each dataset. The scripts will be placed in the evaluation folder of each dataset. Lastly, there is the "plotter.py" script, which can be found in the plotting folder. It creates 36 visualizations that show the performance of various parameters.

The source code of the project is written by Tobias Hajszan and Moritz Staudinger.

The project will only produce structured text in CSV format and PNGs for visualizations.

The CSV format is our go to format for our created data as it is very easy to handle and is deeply integrated into most programming languages, operating systems and environments. Metadata will be added to each generated CSV file with creation date, column names and their datatypes and the used random state seed if applicable.

PNG is used as it is the most used lossless compression image format and is recommended by the W3C.

The ARFF format is needed as one of the external datasets is only available in this dataset. The ARFF file will be converted into CSV format automatically to make the further process more consistent and the file easier to read. The ARFF format contains metadata by design as column names and types have to be defined beforehand. As the fish dataset does not come in ARFF format but CSV, metadata concerning the datatypes will be added to the CSV and will be available in the dataset P4 following the W3C Recommendation: Model for Tabular Data and Metadata on the Web.

The project is split into three main folders: algorithms, evaluation and plotting. In the algorithms folder are the implementations of the algorithms that are compared against the state-of-the-art implementation of sklearn. In the evaluation folder there are two folders for the external datasets: fish and employee. Each of these folders is structured exactly the same, there are the folders data (here will the external data set go) and results (here will the produced results be). Next to these two folders, there is an executable python file named "predictor.py".

The folder structure of the project can be visualized by the list below:

- algorithms
 - gd
 - knn
- evaluation
 - employee
 - data
 - results
 - fish

- data
 - results
- plotting
 - evaluations
 - plots

The procedure and the produced files are described in detail in the README.md file that can be found in the root directory of the project.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in README.md. Version control is automated.

We will be using the following domain specific metadata standards:

- [W3C] Model for Tabular Data and Metadata on the Web

The textual results of the project will be saved in CSV files and will contain the following metadata:

- created field
- column names
- datatypes
- random state (when applicable)

Furthermore, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at dataset and project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

Data quality checks will be done, e.g. checks of consistency of labels, logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 (Training and Test Subsets for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P2 (Results for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P3 (Plots for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P4 (Datasets for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P5 (Source Code for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD) will be stored in ZENODO. External storage will be used because this storage is used additional to the github and zenodo service to provide a private backup location which is decoupled from external services.

P1 (Training and Test Subsets for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P2 (Results for

Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P3 (Plots for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P4 (Datasets for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD), P5 (Source Code for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD) will be stored in Microsoft OneDrive. External storage will be used because this storage is used additional to the github and zenodo service to provide a private backup location which is decoupled from external services.

P5 (Source Code for Performance Comparison of kNN and GD) will be stored in GitHub. External storage will be used because this storage is used additional to the github and zenodo service to provide a private backup location which is decoupled from external services.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to the data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
P4	writing	reading only	reading only
P5	writing	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

Ethical issues in the project have been identified and discussed with the Research Ethics Coordinator at TU Wien (<https://www.tuwien.at/en/research/rti-support/research-ethics/>). They are described in detail in separate documents. The research has not been reviewed yet by any ethics committee.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns. Further data will be made available with restrictive access.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo		CC BY 4.0
P2	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo		CC BY 4.0
P3	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo		CC BY 4.0
P4	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo		CC BY 4.0
P5	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo, GitHub		MIT 3.0

The repository used in this project described in the following paragraph.

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results. <https://zenodo.org/>

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com>

Specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data: all data formats are either images in standardized formats or structured text that can be viewed and used with standard software. To run the experiments python 3 is needed as well as some python libraries listed in the requirements.txt file.

Description of protocol to access restricted data:

5b Long-term preservation and reusability

dataset ID	location for long-term storage (min. 10 years)	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	10 years	Students and general public
P2	Zenodo	10 years	Students and general public
P3	Zenodo	10 years	Students and general public
P4	Zenodo	10 years	Students and general public
P5	Zenodo and GitHub	10 years	Students and general public

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Tobias Hajszan will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Title	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0